

Stimulating risk averse farmers to adopt microbial applications

Annika Francesca Tensi

Business Economics Group, Wageningen University & Research, KN Wageningen, The Netherlands

*Corresponding author: E-mail: frederic.ang@wur.nl

Received: December 23, 2022. Accepted: February 27, 2023

Abstract

Increasing agricultural production, while decreasing its impact on the environment is a global challenge. Sustainable innovations, such as microbial applications, can play an important role in this light. However, risk averse farmers are often reluctant to adopt such innovations. In this study, we investigate (i) the relationship between risk attitude and farmers' intention to adopt microbial applications and (ii) the effectiveness of an informational video to stimulate the adoption. In July 2020, 98 Dutch arable farmers have participated in an online survey with an experiment. In the experiment, half of the farmers have watched an informational video on microbial applications, while the other half was a clean control without receiving information. Then, all farmers are assigned a monetarily incentivised standard Multiple Price List (MPL) and a payoff-varying MPL lottery game to assess the relationship between innovation adoption and risk attitudes. We find evidence that the video has a significant effect on farmers' intention to adopt microbial applications. Further, our results suggest that the intention to use microbial applications can be influenced by farmers' risk attitude.

Keywords: Information Provision, Risk, Probability Weighting, Microbial Applications, Innovation Adoption

JEL codes: C91, D91, Q12

1. Introduction

The agricultural sector is confronted with a dual, intertwined challenge. Demand for food is increasing because of intensifying population pressure. At the same time, agricultural production creates environmental problems. To tackle this dual challenge, agricultural production needs to increase whilst decreasing the associated environmental impact. In light of this, the widespread adoption of sustainable innovations is essential, but the success of introducing such innovations is limited, as evidenced by precision farming technologies (Hüttel, Leuchten, and Leyer 2020) and crop innovations (Ghadim et al. 2005). Farmers' risk aversion is one of the hindering factors for sustainable innovation adoption on the farm (Isik and Khanna 2003; Liu 2013; Menapace, Colson, and Raffaelli 2013; Trujillo-Barrera et al. 2016; Dessart, Barreiro-Hurlé, and van Bavel 2019; Spiegel, Britz, and Finger 2021). This study addresses the research question of how to stimulate risk averse farmers to adopt a sustainable innovation.

We investigate microbial applications as an example of a sustainable innovation. Microbial applications, which are microbial communities of beneficial, naturally occurring microorganisms, can increase crop productivity whilst reducing environmental pressure. The

products are applied to the soil in the area around crop roots as a granulate or as seed coating. The additional workload is limited as the products are applied during the seeding process. Microbial applications fulfil different functions (Philippot et al. 2013). They can increase productivity and the quality of crops, suppress plant diseases, and control pathogens (Singh 2017; Gouda et al. 2018). Microbial applications stimulate biological nitrogen fixation, nutrient uptake (Wezel et al. 2014), phosphate solubilisation, and abiotic stress mitigation (de Souza, Ambrosini, and Passaglia 2015). Despite its benefits, microbial applications are hitherto not widely used in agricultural production.

Evidence shows that visual tools such as videos help to convey complex information (Butler et al. 2020). There have been a few studies investigating the effects of informational videos on the adoption of certain agricultural practices or technologies. For instance, in Vandeveldel et al. (2021), an informational video has been used to increase the awareness and adoption of potato quality enhancing practices. In their study, the video indeed increases the probability of adopting the recommended practice. The authors conclude that videos are apt for spreading information on simple, low-cost agricultural practices that have not been widely adopted (Vandeveldel et al. 2021). While informational videos might stimulate innovation adoption, farmers' risk aversion has been found to be a hindering factor (Liu 2013). This is especially the case for novel technologies, which are usually assessed as riskier than those currently in use (Bougherara et al. 2017).

While Vandeveldel et al. (2021) investigate the effect of the informational video in a developing country on the adoption of an existing farm management practice, we investigate the effect of the informational video on the intended adoption, a novel practice *ex ante* and in a European country. We assess the triangular relationship between (i) the stimulating impact of an informational video, (ii) farmers' risk attitude, and (iii) their intention to adopt microbial applications.

The impact of the video and farmers' risk attitudes are assessed through an online survey, which includes a controlled experiment (see Appendix A for a schematic representation of the survey and experimental design in Figure A1). A randomly selected half of the participants—in total 98 Dutch arable farmers—watched an informational video, while the other half was in a clean control group. In the video, we explain microbial applications and their benefits. In the second part of the survey, we elicit the risk attitudes of all participants—treatment and control group—using two monetarily incentivised Multiple Price Lists (MPL). We use the Holt and Laury (2002) (H&L) protocol and the payoff-varying MPL by Drichoutis and Lusk (2016) (D&L) to elicit risk and probability weighting function parameters.

This study has been conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic.¹ Starting in late 2019, the pandemic has been unprecedented in our modern world and as such provided a natural experimental setting to researchers. As stated in our AsPredicted.org pre-analysis plan,² we wanted to use the novel situation to investigate how the COVID-19 pandemic affects risk attitudes of farmers and the intention to use microbial applications.

Various studies have investigated how detrimental life events and shocks affect individuals' risk attitudes (Andersen et al. 2008; Cameron and Shah 2015; Cassar, Healy, and von Kessler 2017; Banks, Bassoli and Mammi 2020; Bellucci, Fuochi, and Conzo 2020). Most recently, it has been found that weather shocks affect farmers' risk aversion (Falco and Vieider 2022). To date, at least two excellent studies on the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on risk attitudes have been published (Drichoutis and Nayga 2022; Harrison et al. 2022), and numerous studies investigated the effects of the pandemic on agri-food systems and supply chains (Stephens et al. 2020; Coopmans et al. 2021; Meuwissen et al. 2021). Due to financial restrictions we have not been able to collect longitudinal data, which would have enhanced the contribution of this analysis. Further, due to the timing of the survey—just after what we now know marked the first wave in the Netherlands—the variation in our COVID-19 proxies and corresponding conclusions are limited. Therefore, we decided to report the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on risk attitudes and adoption

intentions as secondary analyses. We have kept and analyse the four pre-registered hypotheses, including the ones on COVID-19, but the focus of the discussion is on the remaining hypotheses.

We test four hypotheses. First, we hypothesise that farmers' willingness³ to adopt microbial applications increases after watching the informational video. Second, we hypothesise that exposure to COVID-19 increases risk aversion among farmers. Our third hypothesis is that risk averse farmers are less willing to adopt microbial applications. Fourth, we test whether COVID-19 predicts intended use of microbial applications.⁴

2. Methodology and experimental design

The online experiment consists of three parts.⁵ In the first part, we assess farmers' willingness to adopt microbial applications. The second part contains the incentivised MPL. In the last part, we ask questions on the agricultural operations and impact of COVID-19. In the following, we explain each part in detail.

2.1 Multiple price lists

All subjects are assigned to a randomly ordered sequence of two MPLs. We apply the widely used MPL of [Holt and Laury \(2002\)](#) and the payoff-varying MPL of [Drichoutis and Lusk \(2016\)](#). Despite the widespread use of the H&L MPL for risk elicitation, [Herberich and List \(2012\)](#) and [Drichoutis and Lusk \(2016\)](#) illustrate that it is more suitable for investigating the curvature of the probability weighting function than the curvature of the utility function. The curvature of the utility function signals risk aversion. Both, probability weighting and risk aversion, are a notion of risk. [Drichoutis and Lusk \(2016\)](#), propose a payoff-varying MPL that should be presented to subjects together with the standard H&L MPL to investigate both notions of risk simultaneously and derive more correct risk parameters ([Csermely and Rabas 2016](#)). The MPLs differ in whether payoffs or probabilities are fixed. The two MPLs allow us to elicit whether behaviour is driven by actual risk aversion or by a combined effect with over- or under-weighting of extreme events.

In each MPL, the subjects face ten randomly ordered decision situations, in which they choose between two lotteries, A and B. In both MPLs, lottery A is the 'safe' lottery compared to lottery B, which is 'more risky'. Each decision situation is different and independent of all other decision situations, that is, the decision made in one situation does not affect possible earnings in another.

In the H&L protocol, the payoffs are fixed and probabilities vary in each decision situation. The high payoff in the 'risky' lottery is fixed to €38.50 and to €20 in the 'safe' lottery, whereas the low payoff is set to €1 and €16, respectively (see [Table 1](#)). The probability of the higher payoff increases by 0.1 points in each decision situation.

In the payoff-varying D&L MPL, the probabilities are fixed to 50 percent in every lottery and the high payoffs differ marginally in each decision situation, the MPL provides insights to ten points on the utility function. The high payoffs in the 'safe' lottery vary between €16.80 and €24, whereas they vary between €20.10 and €47 in the 'risky' lottery. In both lotteries, the low payoffs are fixed to €16 and €10, respectively. To match potential lottery earnings with the opportunity costs of Dutch arable farmers, we multiply the earnings of the standard MPLs by ten. Details on how we calculated the opportunity costs are provided in [Appendix B](#).

After subjects have gone through all twenty decision situations, we have randomly selected one of them for actual payment. The subjects have been informed in the invitation e-mail that their participation is monetarily incentivised based on the answers that they provide. The agency that has handled the recruitment of the farmers has also confidentially administered the payments. All decisions and payments are treated confidentially.

Table 1. H&L multiple price list.

Lottery A				Lottery B				EVA	EVB	Difference	Open CRRA interval if subject switches to Lottery B ^a	
<i>p</i>	€	<i>p</i>	€	<i>p</i>	€	<i>p</i>	€	(€)	(€)	(€)		
0.1	20	0.9	16	0.1	38.50	0.9	1	16.40	4.75	11.65	−∞	−1.73
0.2	20	0.8	16	0.2	38.50	0.8	1	16.80	8.50	8.30	−1.73	−0.92
0.3	20	0.7	16	0.3	38.50	0.7	1	17.20	12.25	4.95	−0.92	−0.47
0.4	20	0.6	16	0.4	38.50	0.6	1	17.60	16	1.60	−0.47	−0.13
0.5	20	0.5	16	0.5	38.50	0.5	1	18	19.75	−1.75	−0.13	0.14
0.6	20	0.4	16	0.6	38.50	0.4	1	18.40	23.50	−5.10	0.14	0.40
0.7	20	0.3	16	0.7	38.50	0.3	1	18.80	27.25	−8.45	0.40	0.68
0.8	20	0.2	16	0.8	38.50	0.2	1	19.20	31	−11.80	0.68	0.97
0.9	20	0.1	16	0.9	38.50	0.1	1	19.60	34.75	−15.15	0.97	1.37
1	20	0	16	1	38.50	0	1	20	38.50	−18.50	1.37	+∞

Notes: *p* stands for probability. Last five columns showing expected values and CRRA interval have not been shown to subjects.

^aAssumes Expected Utility Theory; interval is computed by finding the root of the expected utility function using the CRRA specification.

2.2 Survey and experimental procedure

In mid-July 2020, we have contacted 3,000 Dutch arable farmers via e-mail through a specialised market research agency.⁶ Pre-registering sample sizes reduces the degrees of researcher's freedom (Simmons et al. 2021). In our pre-registration, we have indicated to collect 100 observations. To have a safety margin, we have programmed the Qualtrics software such that data collection would close after the 106th complete response. The number of 100 farmers has been dictated by the availability of financial resources to pay out farmers, which is one of the primary reasons for the choice of a sample size (Lakens 2022).

The first part of the survey concerns microbial applications and includes the experiment. Half of the subjects are randomly allocated to watch the informational video. The other half of the subjects, the control group, receives no information. The information in the video is based on expert interviews conducted in 2019/2020 with researchers and companies affiliated with microbial applications for the agricultural sector. Later, agricultural microbiologists and agronomists have validated the informational content and graphical representations in the video. We have solicited a company to produce a professional video.⁷ After the subjects have watched the video, we ask several comprehension questions to test whether they watched it attentively. We also ask whether the subjects have 'ever heard about microbial application in arable farming before the start of this survey'. We use the answer to this question to ensure the clean control. Subjects that answer 'yes' to this question are removed from the control group as a robustness check. Then, we elicit the willingness of the farmer to start or keep using microbial applications (on a scale from 0 to 100). The scale indicates the intention to use microbial applications in the future. In addition, farmers indicate on a scale from 0 to 100 to what extent they trust the efficacy and safety of microbial applications.

Last, we seek information on the agricultural operation and the subject, including information on COVID-19. To assess the impact of COVID-19, we elicit how worried subjects are about the coronavirus (on a scale from one to five) and whether they or someone in their close circle (e.g., family and friends) has been infected with the virus. We ask three debriefing questions, namely whether the subjects have seen the video or have heard from the project before and whether the instructions have been clear. At the end of the survey, subjects can provide their contact details in a separate form to receive the MPL payment. Subjects explicitly consent and the experimenters use no deception. We have received *ex ante* ethical clearance from the Social Science Ethical Committee for the overall PhD project of the first author, which is funded by SIMBA, on 12 June 2020. The research in the current paper has

Table 2. D&L multiple price list: payoff-varying and constant probabilities.

Lottery A				Lottery B				EVA	EVB	Difference	Open CRRA interval if subject switches to Lottery B ^a	
<i>p</i>	€	<i>p</i>	€	<i>p</i>	€	<i>p</i>	€	(€)	(€)	(€)		
0.5	16.80	0.5	16	0.5	20.10	0.5	10	16.40	15.05	1.35	−∞	−1.73
0.5	17.60	0.5	16	0.5	21.70	0.5	10	16.80	15.85	0.95	−1.73	−0.92
0.5	18.40	0.5	16	0.5	23.20	0.5	10	17.20	16.60	0.60	−0.92	−0.47
0.5	19.20	0.5	16	0.5	24.80	0.5	10	17.60	17.40	0.20	−0.47	−0.13
0.5	20	0.5	16	0.5	26.50	0.5	10	18	18.25	−0.25	−0.13	0.14
0.5	20.80	0.5	16	0.5	28.60	0.5	10	18.40	19.30	−0.90	0.14	0.40
0.5	21.60	0.5	16	0.5	31.40	0.5	10	18.80	20.70	−1.90	0.40	0.68
0.5	22.40	0.5	16	0.5	35.40	0.5	10	19.20	22.70	−3.50	0.68	0.97
0.5	23.20	0.5	16	0.5	45	0.5	10	19.60	27.50	−7.90	0.97	1.37
0.5	24	0.5	16	0.5	47	0.5	10	20	28.50	−8.50	1.37	+∞

Notes: *p* stands for probability. Last five columns showing expected values and CRRA interval have not been shown to subjects.

^aAssumes Expected Utility Theory; interval is computed by finding the root of the expected utility function using the CRRA specification.

been approved for *ex post* ethical clearance by the Social Sciences Ethical Committee on 20 February 2023. The online experiment lasts 18 minutes.

2.3 Hypothesis testing

To analyse lottery data and retrieve risk parameters, we investigate the MPLs' switching points. Based on the switching points, we determine observation-specific parameter intervals. From the intervals the respective mid-points are computed with a purpose-built function. We conduct several robustness checks. We use different interval values, namely original values from Holt and Laury (2002) and values from Bellemare (2020).⁸ The *r* values offered by Bellemare and colleagues suggest less extreme risk loving preferences than the midpoints of the constant relative risk aversion (CRRA) interval in Tables 1 and 2. Further, we check for an effect of the order of the lotteries, a treatment effect on risk attitude and violations of monotonicity in lottery choices.

We measure the impact of COVID-19 objective data using four different proxies: cumulative positive cases, number of new cases, hospitalisations, and deceased. All proxies are normalised at the municipal level to the maximum number per 1,000 inhabitants in the period between the outbreak of COVID-19 in the Netherlands and the start of the experiment.⁹ Raw data are retrieved from the RIVM (2021) (*Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu*, Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment).¹⁰

We have pre-registered the analysis for each of the hypotheses as follows. We fail to reject the hypotheses based on a 0.1 α error rate, or $p \leq 0.1$. Generally, two-sample *t*-tests are used to test whether the means of the control group and the treatment group, two hypothetically independent samples, are significantly different from each other. In fact, this is the classic use of a two-sample *t*-test (Livingston 2004). We use Welch's *t*-test instead of Student's *t*-test. The former is more robust especially when the two samples have different variances and sizes (Zimmerman and Zumbo 1993; Delacre, Lakens, and Leys 2017), which is the case here. To test hypothesis 1, we conduct a two-sample *t*-test to compare the intention of farmers to adopt microbial applications in the video treatment group with the control group. Additionally, we correlate trust in the efficacy and safety of microbial applications with the intention to adopt the products. We conduct another *t*-test to compare the mean trust in efficacy and safety in the control group and the treatment group. These are potential channels through which adoption could be stimulated that have not been pre-registered. We did not pre-register a power analysis. In line with Massfeller et al. (2022), we conduct a power analysis for the *t*-test on the stimulating effect of the informational video expecting

a 10 percent treatment effect, normalised with a 0.2 standard deviation. With the resulting Cohen's d ($d = 0.5$), a statistical significance level of $p = 0.1$ and both samples $N = 50$, the two-sample t -test would reveal a power of 0.79.¹¹

Hypothesis 2 is investigated by a correlation analysis with the risk parameters and COVID-19 cases and dismay. In addition, a two-sample t -test investigates the relationship between risk attitude and COVID-19 cases in the close circle. Hypothesis 3 is tested by a correlation analysis in which, we test whether there is a significant relationship between risk parameters and the intention to use microbial applications. To complement the two correlation analyses and to test hypothesis 4, we conduct a regression analysis with the dependent variable being the intention to use microbial applications and with the independent variables being risk and probability weighting parameters, a dummy variable for the treatment group, COVID-19 cases and dismay, and several control variables.

3. Structural model and risk parameters

Structural modelling is intended to establish, which theoretical model maximises the fit with empirical data and can facilitate empirical interpretation (Harrison and Ross 2018). We compare expected utility theory (EUT) and rank dependent utility (RDU). We do not include cumulative prospect theory (CPT) by Tversky and Kahneman (1992) for two conceptual reasons. First, our MPLs do not allow to investigate CPT's loss aversion, since the payoffs are all positive. Second, we focus on investigating risk attitudes and their effect on technology adoption. Even though risk aversion and loss aversion are closely connected, we do not want to investigate loss aversion. CPT usually outperforms EUT in terms of data fit and actual behaviour elicited in the lab (Schmidt and Traub 2002; Tversky and Kahneman 1991). However, there are also studies that question the importance of loss aversion (Gal and Rucker 2018). Other studies imply that CPT's dominance can be attributed to probability weighting rather than to loss aversion. RDU is in this light preferable to CPT (Harrison and Ross 2017).

We have planned to estimate the curvature of the utility and probability weighting function with the data from the MPLs, and to estimate the function parameters to determine observation specific risk attitudes. The approach is described in further detail in Andersen et al. (2008) and the supplementary material of Harrison and Rutström (2008). We have largely followed Drichoutis and Lusk (2016). In the following, we describe the models and maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) procedure, why the MLE did not converge and general problems with structural modelling.

As a basis for both models, we assume that subjects maximise utility and are risk averse. Constant relative risk aversion (CRRA) is formalised as

$$U(x) = \frac{x^{(1-r)}}{(1-r)}, \quad (1)$$

where r is the CRRA coefficient and x the possible payoff in the respective MPL decision situation as fixed by the experimenter. If $r = 0$, then there is risk neutrality, which means that the utility function becomes $U(x) = x$. If $r > 0$, then the payoff x is discounted by the CRRA coefficient and utility decreases, which implies risk aversion. The opposite occurs if $r < 0$, in which case the subject is risk loving. The expected utility EU of a lottery i is then expressed as

$$EU_i = \sum_{k=1}^K (p_k \times U_k), \quad (2)$$

where k denotes the possible outcomes of a lottery ($K = 2$) and p_k the probability of outcome k . The difference in expected utilities is $\Delta EU = EU_i - EU_j$. Subjects switch to lottery B

Figure 1. Probability weighting function $w(p)$ specification of [Tversky and Kahneman \(1991\)](#), Illustrative γ values are portrayed.

when $\Delta EU = EU_A - EU_B + \epsilon < 0$. Thus, from the switching point, we can infer the CRRA interval of the subject and thus the mid-point.

Under EUT, subjects linearly weight probabilities as such that subjective and actual probabilities induced by the experimenter are equal. This assumption is challenged under RDU theory ([Quiggin 1982](#)). Under RDU, we suspect that subjects often ascribe subjective probability weights to true probabilities. We use the specification of [Tversky and Kahneman \(1991\)](#) to describe subjective probability weighting as follows:

$$w(p) = \frac{p^\gamma}{[p^\gamma + (1 - p)^\gamma]^{1/\gamma}} \quad \forall \quad 0 < p < 1. \tag{3}$$

Here, γ is the probability weighting parameter and p the probability of the respective MPL decision situation as ascribed by the experimenter. However, the specification does not behave well at its endpoints and subjects' sensitivity at the endpoints can be overweighted or neglected ([Tversky and Kahneman 1992](#), p. 303). The graph in [Figure 1](#) visualises the intuition of the probability weighting function. When subjects under-weight small probabilities ($\gamma > 1$), the *subjective* probability is lower than the actual probability. When $\gamma < 1$ and subjects over-weight small and under-weight large probabilities, $w(p)$ takes on its typical inverse S-shape. When $\gamma = 1$, $w(p) = p$, and $RDU = EU$. We integrate the probability weighting function $w(p)$ in the expected utility function (Equation 2) and obtain the RDU function of a lottery i .

$$RDU_i = \sum_{k=1}^K (w_k \times U_k). \tag{4}$$

We stick to the CRRA specification of the utility function U_k in Equation (1). Taken together, subjects choose lottery B when $\Delta RDU = RDU(A) - RDU(B) + \epsilon < 0$.

Parameters are estimated using maximum likelihood estimation in line with [Harrison \(2008\)](#), [Andersen et al. \(2008\)](#) and [Drichoutis and Lusk \(2016\)](#). The index ΔEU and observed choices of the subjects are linked through a standard normal cumulative distribution function. We observe the choice y of subject i in decision situation j , where $y_{ij} = 1$

denotes the choice of lottery B and $y_{ij} = 0$ of lottery A. The log-likelihood function thus depends on each subject's choice y_{ij} and estimates of r such that

$$\ln L(r, y) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^J [(y_{ij} \times \ln \Phi(\Delta EU)) + ((1 - y_{ij}) \times \ln \Phi(\Delta EU))]. \quad (5)$$

The same log-likelihood function is applied to estimate the RDU model.

The structural model poses problems for various MLE algorithms in terms of convergence and sensitivity to starting values. We achieve an estimate of $r = 0.546$ ¹² for the EUT function, which is in line with studies on risk attitudes of European farmers (Iyer et al. 2020). We cannot compute reliable estimates for the RDU function. In the RDU model, γ can be estimated ($\gamma = 0.603$) but the related r value is out of bounds ($r = 7.523$).¹³ Possibly, the estimation problems are an artefact of the MPL set-up, as the MPLs do not entail probabilities close to the endpoints (probabilities close to 0 and 1). Therefore, there are no data to fit these steep parts of the function and the information need to be drawn from the less informative, almost horizontal mid-part of the S-shaped curve (see Figure 1). These problems also arise when including observable characteristics (demographic covariates) to the EUT model that control for heterogeneity and should in principle improve the fit. Because of these estimation problems, we only use mid-point risk parameters to analyse our hypotheses in what follows.

We are not the first to report issues when estimating risk parameters with MLE (Just and Just 2016). In Zhou and Hey (2018), the model does not converge in 20 out of 96 cases for three distinct reasons: (i) subjects have been either clearly risk-neutral or risk-loving, then the parameters are not unique, (ii) subjects have not understood the tasks or have responded randomly, or (iii) estimations have hit the bound. We suspect that a combination of these three reasons causes the estimation and convergence issues in our study, too. Monotonicity has been violated eight times in the D&L lottery (8.2 percent) and five times in the H&L lottery (5.1 percent). There are 29 and 12 comprehension failures in the D&L and the H&L lottery, respectively. Similarly, Drichoutis and Lusk (2016) find more monotonicity violations and comprehension failures in their own payoff-varying task compared to the standard H&L lottery. However, even when the observations with monotonicity violations and comprehension failures are excluded, the estimation issues remain.

Gao, Harrison, and Tchernis (2022) suggest to use a Bayesian estimation approach to determine priors and MLE starting values because standard numerical methods often fail to converge. If the log-likelihood function has a plateaued maximum, MLE methods may fail to converge. Also Rommel et al. (2022) find that different conclusions can be drawn from different estimation strategies and that estimates are heterogeneous within and across samples. Nevertheless, they have successfully replicated the results from Bocquého, Jacquet, and Reynaud (2014) and conclude that CPT describes farmers' utility functions better than EUT. Within-sample heterogeneity (as e.g., in Rommel et al. (2022)) indicates that there is not one 'winning' theory, but that some subjects are best modelled by one theory and others by the other, which in practice poses estimation problems (Harrison and Ross 2017).

4. Results

4.1 Sample description and treatment effects

Out of 106 complete responses, eight observations are discarded. We discard one unreliable observation upon serious doubts about the truthful completion of the questions. Seven subjects have watched the informational video before the survey and are therefore excluded from the sample. Subjects in the control group who have watched the video are excluded to ensure a clean control. For subjects in the treatment group, the video might have been

an activating reminder and these are therefore excluded. Further, 20 percent of the farmers indicate that they are using microbial applications and 42 percent mention that they have heard of the innovation before, mostly through specialised farmer magazines. Of these 42 percent of farmers that have heard of the innovation before, 14 are in the control group. We remove these subjects as a robustness check with a modified clean control group. These exclusion criteria and the robustness check have not been described in the pre-registration form, but are necessary for a clean control. The exclusions result in a sample size of $N = 98$ with 50 and 48 in the treatment and control group, respectively. There is no evidence of structural misunderstandings or unperceptive watching behaviour: 97 percent of all questions are answered correctly.

According to Eurostat (2020), 58 percent of all Dutch farmers are 55 years old or older. In our sample, 40 percent of the farmers are 55 years old or older. The 1-sample proportions test reveals that the proportion of farmers aged 55 or older is significantly different from 0.58. Thus, our sample is younger than the general Dutch farming population. Compared to the overall farmer population, where 9 percent have received a full agricultural education and 69 percent have followed a basic agricultural education, our sample is on average more educated. With a total mean utilised agricultural area of 80 ha ($\sigma = 67$ ha), the farms in our sample are larger than the average Dutch arable farms with 60 ha according to 2018 FADN data, but there is also a large variation in the sample. At least one farmer from each province is included. The majority of farmers come from one of the arable-intensive provinces in the North of the Netherlands. The control group and treatment group have similar characteristics. Table 3 lists the overall farm and farmer characteristics and those per treatment group.

Our study falls into the time period of just after what we now know was the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic in the Netherlands. None of the farmers in the sample have been infected with the coronavirus in the period between the start of the lockdown in the Netherlands (13 March 2020) and the start of the distribution of the survey (17 July 2020). However, in this time, there have been no reliable tests or self-tests available. The true number of infections in our sample might be higher. Although the majority of subjects do not know anybody that has been infected, half of the group indicates that they are at least 'worried' about the virus.

According to the RIVM data, on average, there are in total 1.71 cases per 1,000 inhabitants with a maximum number of 8.17 cases per 1,000 inhabitants in the time frame between the outbreak and the survey distribution. Table 4 shows a detailed overview. Subjective and objective measures of COVID-19 in the sample have limited variation.

Average MPL earnings are €22.59 with a maximum of €38.50 and a minimum of €1. Eight subjects have not provided their contact details and have not received their earnings. Eleven subjects have provided their contact details, but have indicated that they do not want to receive the payments. All other subjects have been paid out according to their choice. Regarding the randomised order of the MPLs and decision situations within each lottery, we find no order effect, which means that the data can be pooled.¹⁴ Further, we find no association between the video treatment and switching points.

Risk attitudes are determined by average switching points in the MPLs and the associated mid-point parameters. The subjects switch on average in the fifth row ($\sigma = 3.4$) of the D&L lottery and in the sixth row ($\sigma = 2.9$) of the H&L lottery. Behaviour deviates from risk neutrality as depicted in Figure 2. Accordingly, the mean mid-point CRRA risk parameters are $r = 0.242$ and $\gamma = 0.995$ (which is different in the structural model). This means the farmers in our sample are slightly risk averse and over weight small probabilities.

On average, the intention to keep using/use microbial applications is 55 points. Trust in the safety of the product is 62.68 and in the efficacy is 55.7 as measured on a scale from 0 to 100.

Table 3. Descriptive and summary statistics of farm and farmer characteristics, including information on microbial applications: overall sample and different treatment groups.

Statistic	Overall sample						Treatment group						Control Group								
	N	Mean	Standard			N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Max	
			Deviation	Min	Max																
Male	89					44									45						
Age ^a	98	1,964	10.78	1,940	1,998	50	1,965	11.07	1940	1998	48	1963	10.52	1940	1985	48	1963	10.52	1940	1985	
ha ^b	98	79.57	67.37	0	400	50	75.33	49.08	3	200	48	84.00	82.56	0	400	48	84.00	82.56	0	400	
Full-time ^c	98	0.77	0.43	0	1	50	0.74	0.44	0	1	48	0.79	0.41	0	1	48	0.79	0.41	0	1	
Organic	98	0.11	0.32	0	1	50	0.12	0.33	0	1	48	0.10	0.31	0	1	48	0.10	0.31	0	1	
Organisation	98	0.68	0.47	0	1	50	0.64	0.48	0	1	48	0.73	0.45	0	1	48	0.73	0.45	0	1	
Inhabitants ^d	98	50.36	43.27	6.86	232.92	50	49.14	43.15	6.86	232.92	48	51.63	43.81	10.94	232.92	48	51.63	43.81	10.94	232.92	
<i>microbial applications</i>																					
Intention	98	56.02	31.47	0	100	50	68.22	28.72	1	100	48	43.31	29.34	0	100	48	43.31	29.34	0	100	
Using	98	0.21	0.41	0	1	50	0.26	0.44	0	1	48	0.17	0.38	0	1	48	0.17	0.38	0	1	
Familiar	77	0.51	0.50	0.00	1.00	37	0.68	0.47	0.00	1.00	40	0.35	0.48	0.00	1.00	40	0.35	0.48	0.00	1.00	

Notes: ^aYear of birth ^btotal: own plus leased land ^c76% of the farmers operate their farm full-time and only 12% of the part-time farmers generate less than 40% of their income by farming. ^dIn 1000.

Main crops include ware (20%) and seed potatoes (17%), closely followed by wheat (13%) and starch potatoes (12%).

Table 4. Descriptive statistics of COVID-19 proxies in the sample.

Statistic	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	Max
Worried about corona ^a	96	3.05	1.02	1.00	5.00
Infection in close circle ^b	98	0.32	0.47	0	1
Total cases	98	7.44	6.14	1	32
<i>per 1000 inhabitants</i>					
New cases	98	0.18	0.15	0.04	0.94
Hospitalised	98	0.09	0.11	0.02	0.58
Deaths	98	0.05	0.04	0.00	0.18

Notes: ^aWorry measured on five-point Likert scale, where a three is considered a neutral response, higher values indicate worry, lower values reflect unconcern. ^b0 if no friend or family has been infected, 1 otherwise.

Figure 2. Percentage of safe choices (choosing lottery A) per decision situation and lottery type.

4.2 Relationship between risk, the informational video, and the use of microbial applications

In this section, we follow the structure of the pre-registration. We go step-by-step through each single hypothesis and its pre-registered and additional analyses.

Hypothesis 1: Farmers are more inclined to adopt microbial applications after watching a video explaining microbes in arable farming.

Our results suggest a positive effect of the video on microbial application adoption intentions. The mean intention to adopt microbial applications is significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher in the treatment group ($\mu = 68, \sigma = 28.72$) than in the control group ($\mu = 43.31, \sigma = 29.34$). As visualised in Figure 3, the variation of adoption intention is lower in the treatment group. The findings hold for current non-users and users of microbial applications. The findings also hold and are even more pronounced after removing the subjects from the control group who had some sort of prior knowledge. In the modified control group, the intention to adopt microbial applications is even lower ($\mu = 33.92$). The farmers

Figure 3. Box- and density-plot comparing the intention to adopt microbial applications between treatment groups, including raw data points. (H1).

Figure 4. Relationship between risk attitude and intention to use microbial applications. (H3).

who were exposed to information on microbial applications, but did not watch the video, increased the mean adoption intention of the sample by almost 10 points. This shows that prior information in general increase the adoption intention, but that the informational video is more effective.

The intention to use microbial applications is significantly and positively correlated with the farmer's trust in the efficacy ($cor = 0.86, p < 0.001$) and safety ($cor = 0.74, p < 0.001$) of the innovation. Trust in efficacy and safety is significantly larger in the treatment group than in the control group (efficacy: treatment group $\mu = 60.22, \sigma = 26.69$; control group $\mu = 45.56, \sigma = 26.16$; $p < 0.01$; safety: treatment group $\mu = 71.52, \sigma = 24.60$; control group $\mu = 52.4, \sigma = 30.42$; $p < 0.001$). The relationship between willingness to adopt

Figure 5. Scatterplots visualising relationship between willingness to adopt microbial applications and trust in their safety (A) and efficacy (B). Density plots visualise distribution of trust in safety and efficacy, respectively. Colours indicate different treatment groups. (Related to H1).

Table 5. Correlation matrix of risk attitude and COVID-19 (H2) and willingness to adopt microbial applications (H3) and of COVID-19 and willingness to adopt (H4).

	COVID-19				Willingness to adopt ma	
	Cases ^a		Worried		cor	p
	cor	p	cor	p		
r	-0.021	0.83	0.042	0.68	-0.19	0.06
γ	0.047	0.64	0.060	0.56	0.001	0.99
Willingness to adopt ma	-0.135	0.18	-0.059	0.56	-	-

Note: ^aPer 1000 inhabitants in the same municipality.

microbial applications and trust in safety and efficacy is visualised in Figure 5. Thus, farmers who have watched the informational video are more willing to use microbial applications than those who have not.

An additional power analysis for the *t*-test on the stimulating effect of the informational video has been conducted *ex-post*, even though unconventional. We use the above means of the different control groups and the overall standard deviation to compute Cohen’s *d* ($d = 0.79$). Results reveal that the two-sided *t*-test exhibits a power of 0.98.

Hypothesis 2: Farmers that are more affected by SARS-CoV-2 (coronavirus) are more risk averse than farmers that are less affected.

We investigate the correlation between *r* mid-point estimates and γ estimates with the number of cases, hospitalisations and deceased, and the level of worry. None of the COVID-19 proxies, nor the subjective assessment variables, are significantly associated with the farmers’ risk attitudes (see parts of the results in Table 5). Also, the two-sample *t*-test with farmers who know someone who has been infected and risk attitudes is not statistically significant ($p > 0.1$). For the lack of evidence of a short-term increase of risk aversion as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic, we refute the hypothesis. The results suggest no impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on risk attitudes of farmers in the short-term.

Table 6. Regression results. Dependent variable: intention to adopt microbial applications.

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>	
	intention to use microbial applications <i>cor</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>r</i>	−8.39	0.07*
γ	−6.68	0.29
New cases per 1000 inhabitants	−47.02	0.42
Hospitalisation per 1000 inhabitants	−7.27	0.89
Deceased per 1000 inhabitants	14.70	0.91
Cumulative cases per 1000 inhabitants	3.73	0.45
Corona infected close	−2.04	0.82
Corona worried	1.44	0.74
Age	0.27	0.55
Male	−12.35	0.52
Education: secondary I	38.69	0.32
Education: university	52.56	0.15
Education: secondary II	52.80	0.16
Education: none	70.75	0.09*
Education agri.: practical	−5.06	0.65
Education agri.: basic	−28.77	0.08*
Education agri.: other	−31.35	0.04**
Successor maybe	−2.26	0.84
Successor yes	−0.66	0.96
Organic yes	2.09	0.87
Farmer organisation yes	4.99	0.59
UAA (in ha)	0.02	0.69
Fulltime	−7.89	0.39
Constant	−498.55	0.57
Observations	91	
R ² (Adjusted)	0.28	(0.03)
Residual Standard Error	31.42	(df = 67)
F Statistic	1.11	(df = 23; 67)

Note: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

Hypothesis 3: Farmers that are more risk averse are less willing to adopt microbial applications on their farm.

The correlation analysis reveals that there is a statistically significant ($p < 0.1$), weakly negative correlation between risk attitudes and willingness to adopt microbial applications. In [Figure 4](#), the relationship between the two is visualised and [Table 5](#) summarises the findings. The results suggest that a higher risk aversion is weakly associated with a lower willingness to adopt microbial applications.

Hypothesis 4: COVID-19 is a predictor of the intention to use microbial applications on the farm.

The associations between the number of COVID-19 cases in a municipality and worry about COVID-19 with the intention to use microbial applications are not statistically significant (see [Table 5](#)). Thus, neither is the subjective assessment of COVID-19 found to be associated with the adoption of microbial applications, nor are the objective COVID-19 proxies significantly correlated with the adoption intention. We refute the hypothesis that the degree of being affected by COVID-19 is a predictor of the intention to use microbial applications on the farm.

Instead, the results of the regression analysis in [Table 6](#) suggest that risk attitudes and agricultural education affect the willingness to adopt microbial applications. The more risk

loving a farmer, the more likely that she uses microbial applications. This is in line with our findings for Hypothesis 3. Farmers that have followed a practical education as compared to a full agricultural education are less likely to adopt microbial applications.

5. Discussion

We assess the effect of an informational video on adoption intentions. We find that the informational video increases the farmers' willingness to adopt microbial applications. In this discussion, we focus on the treatment effect and the adoption of microbial applications. We also discuss the potential influence of risk attitudes and COVID-19 on adoption.

The informational video can be compared to nudges and other forms of interventions. With nudges, so-called choice architects or nudgers, aim to gently push people's decisions in a direction that is not exclusively to the benefit of the nudger by exploiting people's cognitive biases (Congiu and Moscati 2022). Our informational video does not exploit such cognitive biases, but only communicates information. However, the distinction between information, nudges, boosts, and even marketing is blurry. For instance, most nudges depend on information (Ölander and Thøgersen 2014) and marketing often makes use of nudging tools (Congiu and Moscati 2022). Also boosts, which enhance the cognitive capacities of people by teaching them more effective decision principles, are based on information (Harrison and Ross 2018). When designing an intervention to stimulate the adoption of sustainable innovations, the entire behavioural intervention tool-kit and the combinations within it should be considered.

For instance, Ouvrard et al. (2020) find that a combination of a subsidy and an informational nudge are more effective than a subsidy alone. They conclude that the dissemination of information on the benefits of a technology increases its adoption, which is in their case a smart water meter. The results of our clean control experiment suggest that informational videos are effective. Videos seem to be particularly useful if one wants to convey a complex message or explain a complex technology. However, further research is needed to compare the effectiveness of information provision to nudges, such as social comparison nudges. Social comparison nudges are the most used nudges in the agricultural context: Treated farmers receive information on how many of their peers have adopted the innovation or practice in question. Results in previous studies on the effectiveness of such social comparison nudges are inconclusive. Kuhfuss et al. (2022) and Massfeller et al. (2022) both find no effect of social comparison nudges.

We recommend to consider the use of informational videos in campaigns on the adoption of sustainable farm innovations, eventually in combination with nudging tools. Informational videos can be a low-cost addition used in extension service. To date, the effectiveness of ICT-based tools, such as videos, has been proven in developing countries (David, David, and Asamoah 2011; Spielman et al. 2021; Vandevelde et al. 2021). These tools are able to raise the impact of extension services (Spielman et al. 2021) and increase the knowledge of farmers (David, David, and Asamoah 2011). A balanced expert panel should validate *ex ante* the information provided in the video. The receiver of the nudge, in our case farmers, should regard the issuer of the video, in our case a university, as an impartial, trusted source (Reddy et al. 2020).

The results suggest that the farmers in our sample are risk averse, which is in line with other studies (Menapace, Colson, and Raffaelli 2013; Iyer et al. 2020, for e.g.). These risk averse farmers are reluctant to adopt microbial applications. We support previous findings that suggest a hindering impact of risk aversion on adoption of innovations (Isik and Khanna 2003). Yet, risk attitudes elicited in lotteries do not always correlate with real world risk-taking behaviour (Rommel et al. 2019). So, considering that the risk attitude data are noisy, further research is needed to confirm that risk averse farmers are more reluctant to adopt innovations. For example, noise can be reduced when the MPL order is not

randomised or subjects indicate in which row they would like to switch. Other explanations than risk are also possible. [Bougherara et al. \(2017\)](#) find that farmers are risk-, ambiguity-, and loss-averse. Ambiguity of microbial applications could have been reduced by the informational video, which in turn increases the farmers' intention to use microbial applications. Similarly, the informational video might have allowed farmers to better evaluate the risk associated with microbial applications, which makes adoption more likely ([Sagemüller and Mußhoff 2020](#)).

The main limitations of this study are directly related to our cross-sectional data. Since we investigate *hypothetical* behaviour at one point in time, first, we cannot reliably state whether the adoption decision relates to real life settings, and, second, whether the treatment effect lasts over time. In *ex ante* analyses of innovations, hypothetical bias problems cannot be easily circumvented. Further, to investigate the long-term effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on risk and innovation adoption, panel data would be needed. The timing of the survey, just after the first wave, has been, in retrospect, not ideal. There is too little variation in the COVID-19-related data. Additionally, our sample is significantly younger than the overall Dutch farming population, which might have influenced our findings. We also acknowledge that we do not correct for multiple hypothesis testing even though we test multiple hypotheses. In future studies, a Bonferroni adjustment should be considered ([Noble 2009](#)).

6. Conclusion

This study investigates the triangular relationship between the stimulating impact of an informational video and farmers' risk attitude on the intention to adopt microbial applications. In addition, we investigate the relationship between innovation adoption, COVID-19 proxies and risk attitude. Our analysis leads to three main findings. First, the video has a significant effect on the farmers' intention to use microbial applications in primary production, independent of the risk attitude of the farmers. Informational videos can be an effective, low-cost tool to stimulate the adoption of innovations such as microbial applications. Extension services can use videos to explain complex practices and innovations. National policy-makers can use videos to explain the goals of the European Farm-to-Fork strategy ([European Commission 2020](#)) and how to reach them. Second, our results suggest that the intention to use microbial applications is influenced by the subject's risk attitude. Third, we do not find evidence that risk attitudes have changed in the short-term after the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic in the Netherlands. However, this is not a causal relationship, just an association, and due to various limitations of this study, this last conclusion is just an indication and further research is needed to test the reliability of this finding. Further, we conclude that especially well educated and risk loving farmers should be the first to approach when bringing microbial applications to the market.

We have several suggestions for future research. First, panel data and a replication of the study are required to measure the difference of risk attitudes during and after the pandemic. We recommend the combined use of the D&L and the H&L lottery. Second, while our study provides important insights into a specific area of research in innovation adoption, follow-up studies should investigate the effectiveness of informational videos beyond increasing the adoption intention of farmers and initiate actual behaviour and innovation adoption *ex post*. Third, the long-term robustness of the video should be tested. The effectiveness and persistent effect of the informational video should be compared with other types of incentives and combinations of nudges.

Acknowledgements

We thank the farmers who participated in the experiment. We acknowledge the experts who contributed to the production of the video and Jan Geelen consultancy for distributing the

surveys. We acknowledge the contribution of Diogo Geraldes to the design of the experiment and the survey. We further thank H. J. van der Fels-Klerx for her feedback on the draft, and Sabine Schnabel and Julian Sagebiel for their help on the estimations. We appreciate the anonymous reviewers for their constructive feedback.

Supplementary material

Supplementary data are available at [Q Open](#) online.

Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 818431 (SIMBA). This output reflects only the authors' view and the Research Executive Agency (REA) cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they do not have known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this study.

Data availability

Participant data cannot be shared due to restrictions set in the experimental instructions. The code is available in the supplementary material and via OSF (<https://osf.io/7gjqwq/>).

End Notes

1. The SARS-CoV-2 (coronavirus) pandemic first emerged in the city of Wuhan, China, at the end of 2019. Causing severe pneumonia, the coronavirus disease (or COVID-19) can be fatal for humans and poses challenges for health care systems all over the world. Being highly transmissible, the coronavirus spread over the world within just a couple of months (Hu et al. 2021). All European countries, including the Netherlands, brought public life to a halt in spring 2020 to limit the spread of the virus.
2. Pre-registration can be accessed via <https://aspredicted.org/at6w3.pdf>.
3. Please note that the words intention and willingness are used interchangeably.
4. In the pre-registration, the informational video is called a 'nudge'. According to Thaler and Sunstein (2008), a nudge is 'any aspect of the choice architecture that alters people's behavior in a predictable way without forbidding any options or significantly changing their economic incentives'. In the current study, the informational video is therefore not regarded as a nudge.
5. Full instructions are included in the supplementary material.
6. The invitations have been sent out on 17 July 2020 and the survey has been open for about one week until the maximum number has been reached.
7. The video is available on YouTube and in the following OSF project: <https://osf.io/7gjqwq/>.
8. The following r values from Bellemare (2020) are applied: $r = -0.95$ is assigned to subjects who switch in the first line of the D&L MPL experiment; $r = -0.49$ to subjects who switch in the second line; $r = -0.15$ to subjects who switch in the third; $r = 0.15$ to subjects who switch in the fourth; $r = 0.41$ to subjects who switch in the fifth; $r = 0.68$ to subjects who switch in the sixth; $r = 0.97$ to subjects who switch in the seventh; $r = 1.37$ to subjects who switch in the eighth; and $r = 1.50$ to subjects who switch in one of the last two lines.
9. Normalisation: i) scan the daily COVID-19 figures of the proxies and retrieve the maximum value in the specified time frame; ii) use the maximum values to compute the normalised proxies per 1.000 inhabitants per municipality; and iii) connect the respective information to each subject.

10. RIVM data on COVID-19 are provided on municipality level. We have not directly collected information on the municipality of the subjects. Yet, as subjects indicate the first three digits of their postcode, we are able to match subjects to municipalities using data from the [Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek \(2019\)](#). Then, we connect the subjects to the RIVM COVID-19 data and inhabitant statistics ([Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek 2020](#)).
11. Computed with the *pwr* R package ([Champely 2020](#)).
12. Same estimate with *bbmle* package ([Bolker and R Development Core Team 2020](#)) and *maxLik* package ([Henningsen and Toomet 2011](#)); starting value of $r = 0.76$, standard error 0.034, $p < 0.001$, $\logLik. = -740.94$ ($df = 1$), AIC: 1483.889, BIC: 1495.664, and 95 percent confidence interval: [0.48, 0.61].
13. Starting values: $r = 0.76$, $\gamma = 0.5$, all covariates = 0; and computed with *maxLik* function ([Henningsen and Toomet 2011](#)).
14. There is no significant difference in the switching points of subjects that first conduct the D&L lottery (switching point H&L lottery $M = 5.74$, $SD = 2.84$; and switching point D&L lottery $M = 4.74$, $SD = 3.53$) and the ones doing the H&L lottery first (switching point H&L lottery $M = 5.63$, $SD = 2.96$; and switching point D&L lottery $M = 4.96$, $SD = 3.35$); H&L switching points: $t(95) = 0.20$, $p = 0.8449$, D&L switching points: and $t(95) = 0.31$, $p = 0.7542$.

Appendix A. Survey Design

Figure A1. Schematic representation of survey and experimental design with sequence of events.

Appendix B. Opportunity cost calculation

According to the European Farm Accountancy Network (FADN) the arable farm net income in the Netherlands in 2018 is €86,695. The farm net income is defined as the ‘remuneration to fixed factors of production of the farm (work, land and capital) and remuneration to the entrepreneurs risks (loss/profit) in the accounting year’. When we divide this yearly income by $52 \times 5 \times 8$, even though we are aware that farming is not a classic 40 hour/week job, we get an hourly wage of €41.66.

At the same time, the family farm income is €73,002, which is defined as the income expressed per family labour unit. It ‘takes into account differences in the family labour force to be remunerated per holding. It is calculated only for the farms with family labour’. Using the family farm income as the basis, we obtain an hourly wage of €35.10.

Family farm income is the better estimate. Since it accounts for family labour, it provides a good proxy for the income per person. The income more than doubled between 2017 and 2018. The average over the last 4 years (2015–2018) is €29.64 (farm net hourly income)

and €19.96 (family farm income, hourly). Both 2019 and 2020 are rather bad years for arable farmers in the Netherlands due to the drought and heat, as well as the corona pandemic (see e.g. potato mountain <https://www.aardappelberg.nl/>). Thus, we use €20 as a benchmark for the one-hour opportunity cost of a farmer. There are no data on the regional differences, but Dutch arable farms are rather homogeneous and no meaningful differences are to be expected.

References

- Andersen S., Harrison G. W., Lau M. L. and Rutström E. E. (2008). 'Risk aversion in game shows', *Research in Experimental Economics*, 12: 359–404.
- Banks J., Bassoli E. and Mammi I. (2020). 'Changing attitudes to risk at older ages: the role of health and other life events', *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 79: 102208.
- Bellemare M. F. (2020). 'How to write well (in economics)', Working Paper, 1–42.
- Bellucci D., Fuochi G. and Conzo P. (2020). 'Childhood exposure to the Second World War and financial risk taking in adult life', *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 79: 102196.
- Bocquého G., Jacquet F. and Reynaud A. (2014). 'Expected utility or prospect theory maximisers? Assessing farmers' risk behaviour from field-experiment data', *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 41: 135–72.
- Bolker B. R Development Core Team. (2020). '*bbmle: Tools for General Maximum Likelihood Estimation*'. R package version 1.0.25, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=bbmle>.
- Bougherara D., Gassmann X., Piet L. and Reynaud A. (2017). 'Structural estimation of farmers' risk and ambiguity preferences: a field experiment', *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 44: 782–808.
- Butler J. M., Fooks J. R., Messer K. D. and Palm-Forster L. H. (2020). 'Addressing social dilemmas with mascots, information, and graphics', *Economic Inquiry*, 58: 150–68.
- Cameron L. and Shah M. (2015). 'Risk-taking behavior in the wake of natural disasters', *Journal of Human Resources*, 50: 484–515.
- Cassar A., Healy A. and von Kessler C. (2017). 'Trust, risk, and time preferences after a natural disaster: experimental evidence from Thailand', *World Development*, 94: 90–105.
- Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. (2019). *Buurt, wijk en gemeente 2019 voor postcode huisnummer*. <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/maatwerk/2019/42/buurt-wijk-en-gemeente-2019-voor-postcode-huisnummer>.
- Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. (2020). *Regionale Kerncijfers Nederland: Gemeente, Lokalisering code, Bevolking*. <https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/70072ned/table?dl=5384E>.
- Champely S. (2020). *pur: Basic Functions for Power Analysis*. R package version 1.3-0, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=pwr>.
- Congiu L. and Moscati I. (2022). 'A review of nudges: definitions, justifications, effectiveness', *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 36: 188–213.
- Coopmans I., Bijtbeier J., Marchand F., Mathijs E., Messely L., Rogge E., Sanders A. and Wauters E. (2021). 'COVID-19 impacts on Flemish food supply chains and lessons for agri-food system resilience', *Agricultural Systems*, 190: 103136.
- Csermely T. and Rabas A. (2016). 'How to reveal people's preferences: comparing time consistency and predictive power of multiple price list risk elicitation methods', *Journal of Risk and Uncertainty*, 53: 107–36.
- David S., David S. and Asamoah C. (2011). 'Video as a tool for agricultural extension in Africa: a case study from Ghana', *International Journal of Education and Development using ICT*, 7: 26–41.
- de Souza R., Ambrosini A. and Passaglia L. M. (2015). 'Plant growth-promoting bacteria as inoculants in agricultural soils', *Genetics and Molecular Biology*, 38: 401–19.
- Delacre M., Lakens D. and Leys C. (2017). 'Why psychologists should by default use Welch's *t*-test instead of student's *t*-test', *International Review of Social Psychology*, 30: 92–101.
- Dessart F. J., Barreiro-Hurlé J. and van Bavel R. (2019). 'Behavioural factors affecting the adoption of sustainable farming practices: a policy-oriented review', *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 46: 417–71.
- Drichoutis A. C. and Lusk J. L. (2016). 'What can multiple price lists really tell us about risk preferences?' *Journal of Risk and Uncertainty*, 53: 89–106.

- Drichoutis A. C. and Nayga R. M., Jr (2022). 'On the stability of risk and time preferences amid the COVID-19 pandemic', *Experimental Economics*, 25: 759–94.
- European Commission (2020). *A Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system*. COM(2020) 381 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex:52020DC0381>.
- Eurostat. (2020). *Agriculture, forestry and fishery statistics: 2020 edition*.
- Falco S. D. and Vieider F. M. (2022). 'Environmental adaptation of risk preferences', *The Economic Journal*, 132: 2737–66.
- Gal D. and Rucker D. D. (2018). 'The loss of loss aversion: will it loom larger than its gain?' *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 28: 497–516.
- Gao X. S., Harrison G. W. and Tchernis R. (2022). 'Behavioral welfare economics and risk preferences: a Bayesian approach', *Experimental Economics*, 1–31
- Ghadim A. K., Pannell D. J. and Burton M. P. (2005). 'Risk, uncertainty, and learning in adoption of a crop innovation', *Agricultural Economics*, 33: 1–9.
- Gouda S., Kerry R. G., Das G., Paramithiotis S., Shin H. S. and Patra J. K. (2018). 'Revitalization of plant growth promoting rhizobacteria for sustainable development in agriculture', *Microbiological Research*, 206: 131–40.
- Harrison G. W. (2008). 'Maximum likelihood estimation of utility functions using Stata'. University of Central Florida, Working Paper, 06–12.
- Harrison G. W., Hofmeyr A., Kincaid H., Monroe B., Ross D., Schneider M. and Swarthout J. T. (2022). 'Subjective beliefs and economic preferences during the COVID-19 pandemic', *Experimental Economics*, 25: 795–823.
- Harrison G. W. and Ross D. (2017). 'The empirical adequacy of cumulative prospect theory and its implications for normative assessment', *Journal of Economic Methodology*, 24: 150–65.
- Harrison G. W. and Ross D. (2018). 'Varieties of paternalism and the heterogeneity of utility structures', *Journal of Economic Methodology*, 25: 42–67.
- Harrison G. W. and Rutström E. E. (2008). 'Risk aversion in the laboratory', *Research in Experimental Economics*, 12: 41–196.
- Henningsen A. and Toomet O. (2011). 'MaxLik: a package for maximum likelihood estimation in R', *Computational Statistics*, 26: 443–58.
- Herberich D. H. and List J. A. (2012). 'Digging into background risk: experiments with farmers and students', *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 94: 457–63.
- Holt C. A. and Laury S. K. (2002). 'Risk aversion and incentive effects', *American Economic Review*, 92: 1644–55.
- Hu B., Guo H., Zhou P. and Shi Z. L. (2021). 'Characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19', *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 19: 141–54.
- Hüttel S., Leuchten M. T. and Leyer M. (2020). 'The importance of social norm on adopting sustainable digital fertilisation methods', *Organization and Environment*, 35: 79–102.
- Isik M. and Khanna M. (2003). 'Stochastic technology, risk preferences, and adoption of site-specific technologies', *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 85: 305–17.
- Iyer P., Bozzola M., Hirsch S., Meraner M. and Finger R. (2020). 'Measuring farmer risk preferences in europe: a systematic review', *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 71: 3–26.
- Just D. R. and Just R. E. (2016). 'Empirical identification of behavioral choice models under risk', *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 98: 1181–94.
- Kuhfuss L., Préget R., Thoyer S., de Vries F. P. and Hanley N. (2022). 'Enhancing spatial coordination in payment for ecosystem services schemes with non-pecuniary preferences', *Ecological Economics*, 192: 107271.
- Lakens D. (2022). 'Sample Size Justification', *Collabra: Psychology*, 8: 33267.
- Liu E. M. (2013). 'Time to change what to sow: risk preferences and technology adoption decisions of cotton farmers in China', *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 95: 1386–403.
- Livingston E. H. (2004). 'Who was student and why do we care so much about his *t*-test?' *Journal of Surgical Research*, 118: 58–65.
- Massfeller A., Meraner M., Hüttel S. and Uehleke R. (2022). 'Farmers' acceptance of results-based agri-environmental schemes: a German perspective', *Land Use Policy*, 120: 106281.
- Menapace L., Colson G. and Raffaelli R. (2013). 'Risk aversion, subjective beliefs, and farmer risk management strategies', *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 95: 384–89.

- Meuwissen M. P., Feindt P. H., Slijper T., Spiegel A., Finger R., de Mey Y., Paas W., Termeer K. J., Poortvliet P. M., Peneva M., Urquhart J., Vigani M., Black J. E., Nicholas-Davies P., Maye D., Appel F., Heinrich F., Balmann A., Bijttebier J., Coopmans I., Wauters E., Mathijs E., Hansson H., Lagerkvist C. J., Rommel J., Manevska-Tasevska G., Accatino F., Pineau C., Soriano B., Bardaji I., Severini S., Senni S., Zinnanti C., Gavrilescu C., Bruma I. S., Dobay K. M., Matei D., Tanasa L., Voicilas D. M., Zawalińska K., Gradziuk P., Krupin V., Martikainen A., Herrera H. and Reidsma P. (2021). 'Impact of Covid-19 on farming systems in Europe through the lens of resilience thinking', *Agricultural Systems*, 191: 103152.
- Noble W. S. (2009). 'How does multiple testing correction work? *Nature Biotechnology* 2009 27:12, 27: 1135–37.
- Ölander F. and Thøgersen J. (2014). 'Informing versus nudging in environmental policy', *Journal of Consumer Policy*, 37: 341–56.
- Ouvrard B., Préget R., Reynaud A. and Nudging L. T. (2020). 'Nudging and Subsidizing Farmers to Foster Smart Water Meter Adoption.
- Philippot L., Raaijmakers J. M., Lemanceau P. and van der Putten W. H. (2013). 'Going back to the roots: the microbial ecology of the rhizosphere. *Nature reviews. Microbiology*, 11: 789–99.
- Quiggin J. (1982). 'A theory of anticipated utility', *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 3: 323–43.
- Reddy S. M., Wardropper C., Weigel C., Masuda Y. J., Harden S., Ranjan P., Getson J. M., Esman L. A., Ferraro P. J. and Prokopy L. (2020). 'Conservation behavior and effects of economic and environmental message frames', *Conservation Letters*, 1–5.
- RIVM (2021). 'RIVM COVID-19 Dataset'. <https://data.rivm.nl/covid-19/>.
- Rommel J., Hermann D., Müller M. and Mußhoff O. (2019). 'Contextual framing and monetary incentives in field experiments on risk preferences: evidence from german farmers', *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 70: 408–25.
- Rommel J., Sagebiel J., Baaken M. C., Barreiro-Hurl J., Bougherara D., Cembalo L., Cerjak M., Čop T., Czajkowski M., Espinosa Goded M., Höhler J., Kuhfuss L., Lagerkvist C., Lapierre M., Lefebvre M., Matzdorf B., Ott E., Paparella A., Quendler E., Rodriguez Entrena M., Schulze C., Šumrada T., Tensi A., Thoyer S., Maksan M. T., Vecchio R., Willinger M. and Zagórska K. (2022). 'Farmers' risk preferences in 11 European farming systems: a multi-country replication of Bocquho et al (2014)', *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy*, 1–26.
- Sagemüller F. and Mußhoff O. (2020). 'Effects of household shocks on risk preferences and loss aversion: evidence from upland smallholders of south east asia', *Journal of Development Studies*, 56: 2061–78.
- Schmidt U. and Traub S. (2002). 'An experimental test of loss aversion', *Journal of Risk and Uncertainty*, 25: 233–49.
- Simmons J. O., Nelson L. D. and Simonsohn U. (2021). 'Pre-registration: why and how', *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 31: 151–62.
- Singh B. K. (2017). 'Creating new business, economic growth and regional prosperity through microbiome-based products in the agriculture industry', *Microbial Biotechnology*, 10: 224–227.
- Spiegel A., Britz W. and Finger R. (2021). 'Risk, risk aversion, and agricultural technology adoption—a novel valuation method based on real options and inverse stochastic dominance', *Q Open*, 1: qoab016.
- Spielman D., Lecoutere E., Makhija S. and Van Campenhout B. (2021). *Information and Communications Technology (ICT) and Agricultural Extension in Developing Countries*. Annual Review of Resource Economics, 13: 177–201.
- Stephens E. C., Martin G., van Wijk M., Timsina J. and Snow V. (2020). 'Editorial: Impacts of COVID-19 on agricultural and food systems worldwide and on progress to the sustainable development goals', *Agricultural Systems*, 183: 102873.
- Thaler R. H. and Sunstein C. R. (2008). *Nudge: Improving Decisions about Health, Wealth, and Happiness*. Penguin Books, New York.
- Trujillo-Barrera A., Pennings J. M. E. and Hofenk D. (2016). 'Understanding producers' motives for adopting sustainable practices: the role of expected rewards, risk perception and risk tolerance', *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 43: 359–82.
- Tversky A. and Kahneman D. (1991). 'Loss aversion in riskless choice: a reference-dependent model', *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 106: 1039–61.
- Tversky A. and Kahneman D. (1992). 'Advances in prospect theory: cumulative representation of uncertainty', *Journal of Risk and Uncertainty*, 5: 297–323.
- Vandavelde S., Van Campenhout B. and Walukano W. (2021). 'Accounting for spillovers in assessing the effectiveness of video messages to improve potato seed quality: evidence from Uganda', *Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 27: 503–34.

- Wezel A., Casagrande M., Celette F., Vian J. F., Ferrer A. and Peign J. (2014). 'Agroecological practices for sustainable agriculture. A review', *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 34: 1–20.
- Zhou W. and Hey J. (2018). 'Context matters', *Experimental Economics*, 21: 723–56.
- Zimmerman D. W. and Zumbo B. D. (1993). 'Rank transformations and the power of the Student t test and Welch t' test for non-normal populations with unequal variances', *Canadian Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 47: 523–39.